

1 **Creativity through embodied movement in expressive activities:**
2 **conceptualising a new pedagogical model**

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27 **Acknowledgments**

28 The first and second authors were hired by grants funded by the Spanish Ministry of Universities
29 through the European Union-Next Generation [Postdoc Margarita Salas 2022-2024 funded by the
30 University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain].

31 **Creativity through embodied movement in expressive activities:**
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33 This work aimed to outline the first stages for the development of a pedagogical model
34 for teaching-learning of expressive content within physical education (creative body
35 movement). Drawing on several suggestions from previous models' conceptualisations,
36 we explore and present the theoretical foundations, practical considerations, and
37 assumptions that align and support their core features. The major theme of the model is
38 that students explore new expressive movements and develop capabilities through
39 expressive games or tasks that nurture their creativity and ease their embodied
40 movements. This implies that teachers should provide students with several resources
41 and stimuli to nurture their creativity. Also, teachers should promote students'
42 embodiment through the exploration of new movements that allow knowing
43 themselves in different movement situations. The affective and cognitive domains will
44 be prominent in this model. The teachers' and students' assumptions, implementation
45 needs, and enactment about how to apply this model are also proposed.

46 Keywords: expressiveness; creativity; Physical Education; Models-based Practice;
47 embodiment.

48

49 Students' involvement in expressive activities (e.g., dance, mime, drama, rhythm) entails
50 several benefits for their development in different learning domains (Bailey et al., 2009).
51 Regarding the psychological and affective domain, expressive activities might contribute to
52 increasing self-esteem (Connolly et al., 2011), gaining self-confidence and creative power
53 (Biasutti & Habe, 2021), and satisfying basic psychological needs (Sevil et al., 2016). The
54 cognitive domain mainly benefits from developing students' divergent thinking through new
55 and original body movements to express feelings or facts (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017).
56 Regarding physical benefits, rhythmical and dance activities contribute to improving physical
57 fitness by increasing strength and aerobic capacity (Connolly et al., 2011). Finally,
58 concerning the social dimension, expressive activities help people to develop non-verbal

59 communication, express emotions, and improve their social skills (Méndez-Giménez et al.,
60 2017; Payne & Costas, 2021).

61 Despite the suggested benefits, expressive activities receive little attention in physical
62 education (PE) (Mattsson & Lundvall, 2013). One of the main reasons is related to the initial
63 teacher experiences, which lead them to feel insecure, discouraged, and poorly qualified to
64 properly address expressive and creative content (Russell-Bowie, 2013). Also, teachers must
65 deal with social stereotypes and prejudices related to heteronormativity, as aesthetic activities
66 have been traditionally associated with females and are less tolerated by males, which is
67 explained by socio-cultural factors (O'Neill et al., 2011). Another reason that explains the
68 marginality of expressive content is the lack of confidence of PE teachers and students to
69 show emotions and communicate thoughts through the body (Torrents et al., 2011).

70 The literature also describes issues related to the pedagogical approaches used in
71 teaching expressive content (Carriedo et al., 2020). Some authors have provided guidance
72 towards the teaching of expressive activities through creativity. For example, Coterón and
73 Sánchez (2013) suggest working on the elements of creativity such as fluency, flexibility, and
74 originality. Torrents et al. (2013) proposed to focus on the kinetic model, descriptive
75 instruction, and metaphoric instruction to promote creativity through dance. Other methods
76 developed in the performing arts field and designed from an artistic and aesthetic approach
77 (e.g., Laban's movement framework created by 1928) have also used creativity for teaching
78 expressive dance and theatre and what is known as 'creative movement' is in part derived
79 from the movement analysis of Laban (Stevens, 2017). This method, alongside others (e.g.,
80 'Technique and movement expression' developed by Marta Schinca in 1978), analyse and
81 work on different elements of human movement and expressive factors (e.g., effort, time,
82 space, intensity, shape, body flow, direction) to improve the technical performance of dancers
83 and actors and increase body, space, and time awareness (Ferrari, 2014; Laban, 1984;

84 Schinca, 2010). Although Laban's method was not developed for pedagogical purposes, it
85 has been adapted to the educational field (e.g., Langton, 2013). Nevertheless, there is a
86 noticeable absence of precise methodologies within the realm of education for supporting
87 teachers to implement expressive content (beyond dance exclusively) from a creative
88 approach. This leads many PE teachers to address the teaching of this content based on tacit
89 knowledge and in an intuitive way (Coterón & Sánchez, 2013).

90 It is argued that in the teaching of expressive content in PE, there is still a dominant
91 use of technical and directive teacher-centred instruction. Despite the educational benefits
92 associated with direct instruction, such as faster content' learning, which in turn increases the
93 students' perceived competence (Amado et al., 2015) or their confidence to show a skill
94 (Cothran & Kulinna, 2006), direct instruction prevents students from achieving the large
95 benefits that the creative approach provides in socioemotional, embodied, physical, and
96 cognitive learning (Payne & Costas, 2021).

97 Whilst creativity is gaining popularity in the teaching of expressive and aesthetic
98 activities (e.g., Neville & Makopoulou, 2021), it is argued that the teaching of some forms of
99 arts (e.g., dance) is sometimes based on students learning dance techniques or styles (Engdahl
100 et al., 2021; Mattsson & Larsson, 2020), which could be because of the traditional and
101 technical approach of PE (Kerner et al., 2018). This focus on technical aspects and sport
102 skills shows the Cartesian Dualism where physical skills are separated from thinking (Standal
103 et al., 2023). This approach is challenged by other contemporary pedagogies that are
104 garnering increasing attention in PE, such as embodiment where subjects are considered
105 unified wholes (i.e., unity of body-mind). Embodiment includes sensations, emotions, bodily
106 expressions, and postures and it helps students gain body awareness and a greater sense of
107 self (Lambert et al., 2022). This embodiment can be indirectly fostered through creativity. As

108 Payne and Costas (2021) explain, ‘creative dance is embodied, that is, there is no separation
109 of mental processes from action, bodily expression, and interactions’ (p. 283).

110 Creativity and embodiment are two approaches that change the traditional tendency of
111 PE focused on physical skills acquisition, direct instruction, and teacher-centered pedagogies.
112 In the last decades, teacher-centred pedagogies in PE have been (or are being) challenged
113 through student-centred methodologies. Models-based Practices (MbP) are gaining traction in
114 this sense (Casey & Kirk, 2021) and in line with the statement of Casey (2014), have become
115 the ‘bookies favourite’ to student-led practices in PE. Casey and Kirk (2021) consider two
116 elements in MbP: the organising center and a multi-model approach. Notwithstanding, some
117 limitations of these MbP are the application of pedagogical models centred on sports teaching
118 beyond the implementation of other contents (such as expressive content), the need to adapt
119 methods to all students (e.g., low-skilled students) or the lack of teacher qualification to apply
120 models (Fernandez-Rio & Iglesias, 2022). In this sense, the purpose of this manuscript is to
121 conceptualise a pedagogical model for being part of a multi-model approach or a teaching
122 program based on pedagogical model(s) along their course. This model could help to
123 overcome some of the above-mentioned limitations.

124 The findings from a recent review highlighted a gap in teaching expressive content
125 through consolidated pedagogical models (Fernandez-Rio & Iglesias, 2022). Addressing
126 these expressive curricular contents through MbP could help practitioners to know alternative
127 methodologies centred on creativity, which aligns with the proposal of Mattsson and Larsson
128 (2020) for PE: moving from technique-based teaching to teaching based on experiences,
129 explorations, and meanings of non-predetermined movements. This paper attempts to address
130 this gap in knowledge that Fernandez-Rio and Iglesias (2022) highlighted by providing the
131 pedagogical and theoretical rationale for developing a pedagogical model for teaching
132 expressive content through a creative approach, which can benefit embodied learning. Before

133 conceptualising the model, we will briefly show the educational policy support for creativity
134 and expressive activities, specifically within PE.

135 **Educational policy support for creative and expressive body movement**

136 This section will provide evidence on how expressive content might serve as a vehicle to
137 accomplish curriculum standards and to help students acquire some knowledge and skills
138 established in international and national educational contexts. At the European level and
139 beyond PE, expressive content contributes to achieving some key competencies established
140 by the European Union for students in European Schools (Council recommendation on key
141 competencies for lifelong learning, 2018). One of these competencies is ‘Cultural awareness
142 and expression competence’, which consists of developing and expressing ideas or feelings,
143 as well as understanding how they are creatively expressed through a range of arts and
144 cultural forms (e.g., theatre, dance, games, arts, or music). Another competence related to
145 expressive content is ‘Entrepreneurship competence’, which consists of nurturing creativity
146 and initiative. This competence includes imagination, strategic thinking, problem-solving,
147 and critical and constructive reflection within evolving creative processes and innovation.

148 Apart from European key competencies, the expressive content also receives support
149 in national PE curricula. For example, National Standards for PE gathered by Shape America
150 (2013), state a need to teach dance and rhythmic activities (including creative movement)
151 from Year 1 to Year 12 grades. Similarly, Australian educational curricula (ACARA, 2022)
152 include rhythmic and expressive movement activities as one of the focus areas within PE in
153 all grades. This area includes creative movement, movement exploration, dance styles, and
154 dance elements, among other content. This creative approach is also shown in the PE
155 curriculum of England (NCPEUK, 2013) which involves working on the expressive,
156 aesthetic, and artistic qualities of movement. Finally, according to the Spanish curriculum for
157 Elementary School (Real Decreto 157/2022) and Secondary School (Real Decreto 217/2022),

158 the development of students' creativity is a pedagogical principle for both stages. More
159 specifically, it is considered that PE has expressive, communicative, and creative purposes.
160 Also, there is a specific area of expressive activities in both curricula, entitled 'manifestations
161 of motor culture', which include traditional dances, expressive techniques, theatre, circus
162 activities, role-playing games, and rhythmic expressive activities.

163 Unlike Spain, other countries only include dance as an expressive physical activity in
164 PE curricula (Mattsson & Lundvall, 2013). An explanation for the lack of other expressive
165 activities apart from dance may be that PE has a gymnastic and sports background (Kerner et
166 al., 2018), which is still noticeable in our days. In fact, O'Connor et al. (2022) have recently
167 proposed a new classification of sports, including the category of 'rhythmic or aesthetic
168 sports' composed of activities such as rhythmic gymnastics, sport aerobics, dance, or hip/hop.

169 **What about expressive content in Models-based Practice?**

170 MbP implies the use of pedagogical models according to the learning purposes that students
171 should achieve, aligned with Casey & MacPhail's (2018) suggestion to adopt multi-model
172 teaching programmes. Notwithstanding, an isolated model is not capable of adapting to the
173 different national contexts or promoting all learning required in the PE curricula (Lund &
174 Tannehill, 2010). The broad range of context and learning involves teachers' challenges in
175 designing quality programmes, and a multi-model approach could help to organise their PE
176 teaching process (Haerens et al., 2011).

177 The most widely implemented models are related to students' learning of sport
178 content such as sport education or teaching games for understanding models (Casey & Kirk,
179 2021). Consequently, authors such as Haerens et al. (2011) or Williams and Wainwright
180 (2016) have made efforts to afford pedagogical models linked to the teaching of health or
181 adventure content respectively, supporting the possibility of designing a multi-model

182 approach. Revising the main research around pedagogical models (Casey & Kirk, 2021;
183 Metzler, 2017), no specific pedagogical model for the teaching-learning of expressive content
184 has been identified. It is noteworthy that some authors have implemented these expressive
185 contents through other non-specific models such as sport education (e.g., Méndez-Giménez et
186 al., 2017; Richardson & Oslin, 2003), teaching games for understanding (e.g., Levenberg et
187 al., 2020) or cooperative learning (e.g., Darginidou & Dimitris, 2017), but their teaching
188 through MbP is still a gap in the literature (Fernandez-Rio & Iglesias, 2022). To our
189 understanding, the conceptualisation of a specific pedagogical model to teach expressive
190 content could provide teachers with a ‘pedagogical tool’ to reinforce multi-model approach.

191 **Generating a pedagogical model for teaching and learning expressive content:**
192 **Creative body movement**

193 This section groups the first steps to configure a model for the teaching-learning of
194 expressive content drawing on Haerens et al.’s (2011) directions to characterise their health-
195 based PE pedagogical model. These authors grounded this pedagogical model based on the
196 elements described by Metzler (2017) to characterise a model: foundations (including major
197 theme, rationale or domain priorities), teaching and learning assumptions, and
198 implementation needs (see Figure 1). Relevant studies in the field such as Casey and Kirk
199 (2021) have also been used as a guide.

Figure 1. Elements of the CBM.

200

201 ***The major theme***

202 The major theme of creative body movement (CBM) is defined as students exploring new
 203 expressive movements and developing capabilities through expressive games or tasks that
 204 nurture their creativity and ease their embodied movements. This theme implies that teachers
 205 will provide their students with several tactile, visual, and/or auditory stimuli to foster their
 206 students' creativity through the exploration of new body movements or the non-conventional
 207 use of the stimuli (Pickard & Maude, 2021). One of the focuses of this model is promoting

208 students' expression through creativity instead of exclusively enhancing their technical
209 capabilities for dancing, drama, and other expressive and art modalities.

210 Given the major theme of CBM is strongly linked to creativity, it is necessary to
211 understand its meaning and to know why and how creativity is integrated into this model.
212 Considering Hernández-Torrano and Ibrayeva's (2020) study, the standard definition of
213 creativity includes originality and usefulness. Originality refers to novelty, infrequency, and
214 uniqueness, whereas usefulness relates to utility, appropriateness or fit in a specific context.
215 In this model, usefulness should not be understood as an instrumental approach to creativity
216 that looks for a valuable result, but as the appropriateness to a given task or game (e.g., if
217 students are asked to dance with a ball, any action different from this request could be
218 original, but not useful). In recent years, creativity within the scope of education has certainly
219 gained traction (OECD, 2019), as it is deemed one important indicator of education's longer-
220 term outcomes (Tienken, 2016) and a key cognitive skill in an increasingly complex,
221 uncertain, and ever-changing world (Hernández-Torrano & Ibrayeva, 2020). Several scholars
222 have associated the development of creativity, and divergent and critical thinking in
223 educational contexts with economic, social, and cultural prosperity (e.g., Tienken, 2016).

224 Indeed, creativity is also gaining popularity in PE with the implementation of
225 creativity approaches (e.g., Creative Physical Education, Kokkonen et al., 2019) through
226 consolidated MbP such as sport education. However, there are still few studies focused on PE
227 and creativity (Welch et al., 2020), despite it is a subject with great potential for promoting
228 creativity and other cognitive skills (e.g., self-awareness, problem-solving, self-regulation,
229 memory) according to a recent report from the OECD (2019). This is explained because PE
230 allows movement exploration and play (Neville & Makopoulou, 2021) and there are endless
231 movement possibilities (Griggs, 2009). Thus, PE is an ideal scenario for promoting creativity
232 through several games and content. Pickard and Maude (2021) give some ideas about how to

233 foster creativity through beanbag games or by using other materials (e.g., balls, balloons,
234 scarves). For example, we can ask students to pass a beanbag from hand to hand in several
235 ways and invite them to explore new movements or passes.

236 Another possibility for conducting a creative approach in PE is through expressive
237 games and activities (Engdahl et al., 2021; Neville & Makopoulou, 2021; Ørbæk &
238 Engelsrud, 2020), which is the specific content addressed in CBM. Creativity can be
239 especially fostered through expressive activities where students are encouraged to explore
240 their expressive resources and create new and personal movements in unpredictable situations
241 (Engdahl et al., 2021). Also, CBM should seek to go further in the students' development of
242 creativity as a personal value transferable to other contexts, as educational approaches based
243 on motor creativity influence the overall development of creativity (Biasutti & Habe, 2021).

244 The main theme of CBM is supported by the statement that all people have an innate
245 creative potential that can be nurtured and developed in school settings (Kampylis and Berki,
246 2014). This statement differs from the traditional consideration that creativity is a rare gift
247 characteristic of talented or gifted people (Konstantinidou et al., 2014). Thus, this model aims
248 to exploit the creative potential of students in the school context and, specifically, within PE
249 through expressive activities. In this way, children are encouraged to broaden their repertoire
250 of movements and embodied experiences. More specifically, CBM refers to motor creativity,
251 which is the ability to create original movement patterns or new ways to express an idea or
252 emotion through the body (Biasutti & Habe, 2021). Motor creativity is highly task-specific
253 and includes performing arts, sports, and other types of physical activity (Torrents et al.,
254 2021). Creativity in this model also aligns with student-centred pedagogy, as it promotes their
255 active participation during the lessons. According to Pickard and Maude (2021), this
256 approach focuses on 'developing children's capacity to become highly active explorers of

257 knowledge, ideas, and strategies,' (p.3). This pedagogy breaks with the technician-oriented
258 pedagogies based on tracking, measurement, and accountability (Pickard & Maude, 2021).

259 In addition to the conception of creativity in this model, it is also important to explain
260 how expressiveness is understood in this model. Expressive activities in this model are
261 mainly based on the pedagogical discourse proposed by Mattsson and Lundvall (2013),
262 which emerges from the knowledge area of 'dance as expression' which emphasises
263 embodied senses and feelings. This approach is also phrased in terms of rhythm and
264 expressiveness from the student's inner perception of movements instead of being centred on
265 the acquisition of skills related to physical fitness through dance (Mattsson & Lundvall,
266 2013). According to these authors, this pedagogy is 'founded on the idea of the 'body as
267 subject' and valued embodied aesthetic experiences' (p.12). This conceptualisation is also
268 supported by Payne and Costas (2021) who consider that 'creative dance is more than
269 exercising the body, as it connects body with mind in a holistic process of learning' (p. 278).
270 In this line, Torrents et al. (2021) argue that the process of motor creativity is embodied. The
271 term 'embodiment' has a large variety of definitions that refer to the experience of
272 consciousness through the body, which forms a unity with the mind (Lambert et al., 2022).
273 Thus, embodiment implies living in the body, which is the place where learning happens. In
274 this model, creativity will foster the embodiment through the exploration of new movements,
275 which can contribute to students' development of body awareness and may help them to
276 become motivated (Aartun et al., 2022). Within the embodiment, the term movement
277 capability plays an important role, as it helps students to know themselves in movement
278 (Standal & Bratten, 2022). The main intention of some activities such as dance should be
279 students' inner experience while they move in different ways. Thus, the focus should be
280 placed on students' own experience of moving and being themselves in movement rather than
281 learning or perfecting specific dance techniques (Standal & Bratten, 2022).

282 ***Theoretical foundations***

283 As creativity plays a key role in this model, it is important to note what type of creativity is
284 intended to be nurtured on CBM. This model aims to encourage the mini-c level from the
285 Four C Model of Creativity (Kaufman et al., 2022). Mini-c, which is the starting point of
286 higher levels of creativity (i.e., little-c, Pro-c, and Big-c), can be promoted by teachers to
287 increase creativity growth among students in their daily routines. It refers to the individual
288 creativity that is inherent in the learning process and is present in students' everyday learning
289 of any curricular content (Kaufman et al., 2022). As these authors state, creativity should not
290 be seen as something extraordinary at the mini-c level, but as the personal creative insights
291 and interpretations of students in their learning. On the contrary, the big-c level is associated
292 with eminence creativity and the creation of new inventions (e.g., eminent opera composers),
293 the pro-c level implies professional creativity and expert-level creativity that has not yet
294 attained legendary status (e.g. a violinist in the first chair of the Los Angeles Philharmonic),
295 whereas the little-c level refers to daily creativity that implies important contributions to
296 some fields of knowledge despite not being experts (Kaufman et al., 2022).

297 CBM is also founded on the Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2018) due to
298 their support of the students' basic psychological needs satisfaction (i.e., competence,
299 autonomy, and relatedness) (Ryan & Deci, 2018). Following the central tenets of this theory,
300 the satisfaction of basic psychological needs helps to enhance positive human development
301 and wellbeing. CBM is intended to foster a sense of competence to increase students'
302 confidence to express themselves autonomously and to acquire skills that help them to
303 communicate feelings and thoughts. The students' confidence to express themselves implies
304 the development of their body awareness by exploring different movement possibilities
305 through embodied experiences (Aartun et al., 2022) which facilitate the acquisition of several
306 motor competencies and the motivation to engage in physical activity practice. Autonomy

307 would be satisfied through the involvement of students in creative tasks that could promote
308 their decisions to make creations or express themselves autonomously. Finally, relatedness
309 would be satisfied through group tasks where they must create several expressive actions and
310 movements and communicate with their peers through verbal and non-verbal language.

311 Beyond the three aforementioned basic psychological needs, some scholars consider
312 that novelty could be another need within the Self-Determination Theory that contributes to
313 wellbeing (González-Cutre et al., 2016). Novelty, which is one component of creativity
314 (Hernández-Torrano & Ibrayeva, 2020), refers to ‘experience something not previously
315 experienced or deviates from everyday routine’ (González-Cutre et al., 2016, p.3). This
316 potential basic psychological need exerts an essential role in terms of creativity as children
317 are exposed to novel experiences or activities that could promote their creative responses.
318 Novelty has positive consequences for intrinsic motivation (Fierro-Suero et al., 2020), which
319 in turn increases creativity among students (Kaufman et al., 2022). This model is intended to
320 foster novelty through innovative and original proposals and stimuli that lead students to
321 experience new activities and discover their creative potential to come up with novel and
322 original movements to express themselves.

323 Finally, it is important to highlight, as presented earlier, this model's contribution to
324 several learning domains (Bailey et al., 2009). Most PE teachers and PE programmes,
325 however, focus on developing competencies in the physical domain, probably because of the
326 traditional disciplinary mastery orientation to PE where physical exercise is the dominating
327 principle (Haerens et al., 2011). Thus, it is important to focus on developing other domains
328 that do not seem to receive the same attention. For example, in expressive and creative
329 activities, the affective domain has an important role (Biasutti & Habe, 2021) due to students
330 must share ideas using their bodies and creativity to produce inspiration (Garrett, 2022).

331 CBM seeks to promote the holistic development of all the domains, being affective
332 and cognitive domains prominent in teaching-learning. First, the cognitive domain will be
333 enhanced through the development of creativity and divergent thinking in challenging tasks.
334 Also, bodily forms of expression would promote embodied cognition (Neville &
335 Makopoulou, 2021) and help children to develop complex forms of understanding and
336 thinking (Biasutti & Habe, 2021). Second, the affective domain focuses on students' feelings
337 and attitudes, both essential to communicate emotions or sensations through movement
338 within expressive activities. Within the affective domain, expressive activities enhance self-
339 confidence (Marquis & Metzler, 2017). In line with this, Garrett (2022) explains that
340 affective intensities of embodied and creative approaches help students to take risks,
341 overcome fears and be more engaged with their learning.

342 Moreover, expressing feelings via body movements holds a cathartic effect with
343 positive outcomes on psychological health (Cofini et al., 2018) and could help students with
344 communication or language difficulties to express themselves (Sengupta & Banerjee, 2020).
345 Expressive activities take part in the communicative process through non-verbal language
346 and foster the respect and acceptance of others, so inherently this model would support the
347 social domain. In this regard, the idiosyncrasy of the CBM also requires the physical
348 involvement of the students and the knowledge of their bodies (Schwender et al., 2018).

349 ***Teaching and learning assumptions***

350 In this section, we propose several key aspects that should be incorporated into the teaching-
351 learning process of CBM. Its implementation should nurture motor creativity, foster
352 embodiment, ensure the holistic development of all domains (affective and cognitive mainly),
353 as well as the satisfaction of students' basic psychological needs (Ryan & Deci, 2018).

354 To enact this model, the first assumption is to promote a creative environment, letting
355 children make their own decisions. Students must actively explore new movements and ways

356 of expression and respond imaginatively to several stimuli to create ideas (Engdahl et al.,
357 2021), both individually and with their peers. It could be difficult for students to accomplish
358 this assumption the first time they engage in CBM, but they should progressively acquire the
359 ability to propose creative responses to the given opportunities. To this end, CBM must be
360 related to creative pedagogy that challenges students and requires problem-solving,
361 flexibility, improvisation, or adaptation to new stimuli (Engdahl et al., 2021; Mattsson &
362 Larsson, 2020), instead of mainly using methods based on the reproduction of movement
363 patterns or dance steps that currently seem to dominate the teaching of expressive activities.
364 This might be explained because the creative process is inherently risky and unpredictable
365 (Kampylis & Berki, 2014), or because the tradition of teaching abilities through sport-
366 techniques within PE is transferred to expressive activities, which are linked to the functional
367 perspective of movement (Mattsson & Larsson, 2020). Practices exclusively applying
368 directive methods and technique-oriented teaching could thwart the students' creative
369 potential because they are mainly based on replicating technical skills and following
370 teachers' directions (Engdahl et al., 2021).

371 Thus, the second assumption implies that students must have enough time to explore
372 and make their own decisions, rewarding their curiosity and exploration during the lessons
373 (Griggs, 2009) and developing body awareness. Time is necessary for students to explore and
374 discover their own responses based on movement and developing body awareness and
375 embodiment (Aartun et al., 2022), and to gain confidence to express themselves. However,
376 teachers should supervise students' decisions to avoid hierarchies (Mattsson & Larsson,
377 2020), as shy or less creative students could replicate or follow the ideas proposed by other
378 leaders or more creative ones. Students should be able to express themselves in a natural way
379 (roots of the movement), exploring their expressive resources without following standardised
380 patterns of movement (Pickard & Maude, 2021). Teachers should consider the personal,

381 environmental, and task constraints (i.e., boundary conditions and limitations) that can
382 influence action possibilities and students' creative behaviors (Torrents et al., 2021).

383 The third assumption is that teachers or peers must provide students with a balance of
384 appropriate support and challenge (Pickard & Maude, 2021), enhancing their feeling of
385 competence. Teacher or peer-to-peer support can be provided through feedback (Ferriz et al.,
386 2021) encouraging them to participate actively and valuing the (creative) responses,
387 movement exploration, and efforts. This feedback can foster the student's creativity
388 development (Kaufman et al., 2022). Also, the tasks performed by students should encourage
389 realistic risk-taking (Griggs, 2009). In this sense, teachers could introduce strategies to
390 nurture the students' feeling of competence (e.g., to recognise the value of their effort and
391 progress; Ferriz et al., 2021). Moreover, students must be implicated in promoting their
392 awareness of how to express themselves in different situations and the implications of their
393 affective learning (Biasutti & Habe, 2021). Pedagogical implications such as time to discuss
394 the significance of their movement capabilities and their embodiment to convey emotions and
395 ideas are essential to foster body awareness.

396 Finally, the last assumption consists in providing students with meaningful and
397 motivational practices (Griggs, 2009) to enhance the social value of expressiveness.
398 Corporeal practice gives information about the student's feelings or thinking in a natural
399 communicative process. The teacher can design activities implying individual body
400 awareness, but also the expressiveness to other classmates or people beyond PE lessons.

401 ***Implementation needs and enactment of CBM***

402 Following previous research on implementing models (e.g., Fernandez-Rio & Iglesias, 2022),
403 teachers' knowledge and/or training in the content and the model applied are essential to
404 enable students to achieve the intended outcomes. On the one hand, as Payne and Costas
405 (2021) state, teachers need to be trained in the creative movement to be confident in teaching

406 it. Also, the training is important to know how to address the elements of motor creativity and
407 design appropriate tasks. However, teachers do not need professional training in expressive
408 techniques or dance styles, as this model is not based on teaching technical movements. Thus,
409 it facilitates teachers' implementation of CBM within other activities requiring students'
410 expressiveness such as symbolic games. On the other hand, for PE teachers to adapt the
411 model to their educational context, it is necessary to create professional learning
412 opportunities that show how PE curricula are grounded in implementing pedagogical models
413 (Haerens et al., 2011). Collaboration between teachers and researchers could support the
414 successful implementation of pedagogical models influencing positively on their professional
415 development (Goodyear & Casey, 2015). Thus, it could help to transfer theory to practice and
416 overcome constraints when implementing a model for the first time (Casey, 2014).

417 Expressiveness must come from the student autonomously and spontaneously. Their
418 autonomy should be acquired progressively and supported by teachers as essential elements
419 of the teaching-learning process to promote responsible behaviours (Quennerstedt, 2019). It
420 is necessary to withdraw from methods requiring the students' independence without a
421 previous teaching process ensuring the acquisition of basic content knowledge on students.

422 In the application of CBM, teachers must ensure the achievement of the intended
423 educational outcomes and adapt their teaching process depending on the grade of the
424 students, confidence among them, students'/teachers' previous experiences with expressive
425 content, and students' abilities or motivation. To facilitate the transference from theory and
426 practice and ease the implementation of CBM, a general proposal guide is shown below.

427

428 **Enactment**

429 To understand how to implement this model based on the theoretical framework previously
430 explained, we will provide information about practical guidance. Firstly, indicators of motor

431 creativity are explained and exemplified in Table 1. These indicators, which are the most
 432 widely used to assess motor creativity by reference authors in the field (e.g., Bertsch, 1983;
 433 Torrance, 1981), will be encouraged through this pedagogical approach during the sessions.
 434 Table 1.

435 *Indicators of creativity, definitions, and examples*

Indicators	Definition	General example
Fluency	Ability to produce numerous and alternative ways of moving.	Ask students to move in many possible ways with fluency, without spending too much time thinking about a response (movement). The students present fluency when giving many answers in a short time.
Originality	Ability to move in a novel, unique or unusual way.	Develop new and unknown activities for children that promote original, non-conventional or unusual responses in comparison with their peers.
Flexibility	Ability to create responses of several categories. Each movement is quite different from any previous motor response.	Provide students with several objects and ask them to use them in a variety of non-conventional ways.
Imagination	Ability to imagine, empathise, fantasise, and assume unaccustomed roles.	Develop dramatised games and situations through motor stories where students must adopt several roles.

436

437 Apart from nurturing motor creativity (individually and collectively) through the
 438 proposed activities, some strategies to satisfy basic psychological needs must be addressed.
 439 Also, embodiment and movement capability should be indirectly worked on during the
 440 sessions by inviting students to explore and create new movements or to gain awareness
 441 about the ways they move and express themselves. A session layout will be proposed to
 442 guide practitioners in the implementation of the model (Figure 2). This scheme intends to
 443 favor the educational purpose of the CBM, and the enhancement of the students' creativity
 444 supported by the teacher as a facilitator of learning (Goodyear & Dudley, 2015). The
 445 pedagogical need for each phase of the session will be explained and supported by literature.

Figure 2. Proposed session structure of CBM

446

447 1. Group disinhibition/initiation: Sessions must begin with low emotional expressiveness
 448 tasks. Teachers must participate actively at the beginning of the lessons through directive
 449 methodologies (but not stereotyped or technically rigid movements) to promote disinhibition
 450 and allow students to get some ideas about ways of expression. By following or repeating the
 451 teachers' actions or expressions, students can learn several movements and feel secure to be
 452 spontaneous and creative in subsequent activities (Mattsson & Larsson, 2020; Ørbæk &
 453 Engelsrud, 2020). Apart from disinhibition games, teachers can conduct initiation tasks to
 454 introduce the expressive content they intend to teach in the lesson (e.g., rhythmical aspects of
 455 the movement). This part of the session implies a form of teacher-centred instruction, which
 456 can be appropriate in specific situations (Barker et al., 2017), especially at the beginning of
 457 expressive content teaching to ensure a positive perception in students (Amado et al., 2015).
 458 An example of this part could be that the teacher does several dance steps, gestures or body
 459 movements and asks their students to repeat the movements, all at the same time. These
 460 movements can belong to any category (e.g., moving as an animal or a means of transport) or

461 can be varied according to teachers' instructions (e.g., exaggerating the teachers' movements
462 or doing the teachers' movements in slow motion).

463 2. Improvisation and spontaneity: After fostering the students' disinhibition, they will
464 be provided with multiple opportunities and stimuli that encourage them to improvise and
465 give a natural response (i.e., a personal response not biased by stereotypical or socially
466 expected movements). Biasutti and Habe (2021) found that PE teachers consider that
467 improvisation has potential as it contributes to building self-confidence and enhances
468 creativity development, which is in line with the idea of Neville and Makopoulou (2021) who
469 state that creative thinking can be nurtured through activities that require improvisation. Also,
470 creative improvisation tasks can challenge and enable students to take risks, try new
471 movements, and generate knowledge (Pickard & Maude, 2021). In this part of the session,
472 students are divided into small groups and the teacher provides them with several stimuli to
473 promote their improvisation (e.g., several objects to dance with them or everyday sounds -
474 mobile phone ringtones- to dance to the rhythm of these sounds).

475 3. Creative composition: Students will work in groups to create a very short sequence
476 of movements, gestures, and/or positions that nurture their creativity. According to Torrents
477 et al. (2013) and Amponsah et al. (2019), collaborative and cooperative learning promotes
478 creative learning, as children learn from their peers and share divergent thinking. The teacher
479 should propose challenging activities in this phase, as they can enhance group cohesion and a
480 sense of learning as a shared activity (Garrett, 2022). Students should be autonomous in
481 creating their own solutions to expressive assignments, and responsible for performing the
482 tasks and accomplishing group purposes. The teacher's implication is a need as they must
483 continuously supervise the work of all groups and inspire them, especially helping those with
484 more difficulties to come up with new ideas. Also, the teacher must provide their students
485 with varied stimuli to create a composition and new movements. For example, the teacher

486 can use a soundtrack to ask their students to compose a dance with daily actions (e.g.,
487 brushing their teeth) following the rhythm of the track.

488 4. Group exposition (optional): As in the work of Mattsson and Larsson (2020), each
489 group can show their classmates what they created in the previous activity. The exposition is
490 optional and can be introduced in the last lessons when the students feel more self-confident
491 and have a closer relationship with their peers. However, should be teachers who decide if it
492 is appropriate to include this part or what occasion is the best for that. After the exposition, it
493 is possible to come back to another creative composition. The teacher can propose a new
494 activity and ask their students to create a new composition that can be exhibited again to their
495 peers. This exposition should not be understood here as a professional performance or
496 instrumental finality of the creative approach. In the educational context, the process and
497 inner experience of the students while taking part in creative activities are more important
498 than the result (Engdahl et al., 2021). Despite this, the exhibition of the group creation could
499 entail several benefits. According to Montálvez (2012), exposition can be motivating for
500 students and enhance social cohesion as they feel satisfied and proud of their creation,
501 learning, and exhibition of a common 'project'. Thus, relatedness as a basic psychological
502 need might be satisfied. Also, it is a way to learn from their peers' ideas and movements,
503 which in turn can foster the creativity of the observers. Finally, considering that embodied
504 experiences are characterised by sharing, students would have the opportunity to share
505 movement experiences with others, in relation to others, and in the presence of others
506 (Lambert et al., 2022). This exhibition could also help them gain abilities to observe the
507 bodies of others in a relational, perceptive, and empathetic way (Lambert et al., 2022). Thus,
508 this approach provides them with opportunities to know themselves and create new ways of
509 movement based on their inner and shared experience. However, despite these potential
510 benefits, it is convenient that this part is optional depending on the group or the session of the

511 unit, as children might feel judged or ridiculed by their peers when they show their creations
512 (Amado et al., 2015), which can lead them to feel discomfort.

513 5. 'Think about' (optional): This reflection time could allow students to think about
514 their creativity, the exploration of new movements, and movement capability during the
515 session. Reflection plays an important role in PE (Aartun et al., 2022) and several
516 pedagogical models emphasise the need for reflection to encourage their students' awareness
517 concerning some specific learnings (e.g., teaching games for understanding the learning of
518 tactics of sports) or social/personal outcomes (e.g., teaching for personal and social
519 responsibility to reflect and evaluate their responsibility during the lesson). This phase could
520 help students to raise awareness about their body possibilities, to know other possibilities
521 learned from their peers, as well as identify social and cultural facilitators and hindrances.
522 Thus, teachers could ask different questions to favor the emergence of reflections about how
523 socio-ecological conditions (e.g., social stereotypes, heteronormativity, body/expressive
524 movements associated with a culture) influence their creativity and expressiveness through
525 their bodies. This reflection can be done verbally in groups or individually through diaries or
526 other graphic materials where students express their thoughts and reflections. As this phase is
527 optional, teachers can use it according to their educational purposes.

528 **Discussion and conclusions**

529 This work should be understood as a preliminary step in developing a pedagogical model for
530 teaching expressive content in PE, which is based on creativity through embodied
531 movements. It means that creativity and embodied experiences can be promoted through
532 expressive activities (e.g., expressive dance) and symbolic or rhythmical games. CBM tries to
533 address a gap in PE by providing practitioners with a specific pedagogical approach based on
534 literature review and educational policy support. The major theme, theoretical foundations,
535 teaching-learning assumptions, needs, and enactment of the CBM are described.

536 Although other methods for the teaching of expressive dance and movement are
537 present in the literature, such as those developed by Laban and Schinca in 1928 and 1978
538 respectively, they differ from the pedagogical model proposed in this article. While the CBM
539 emanates from a pedagogical approach, the mentioned authors developed their proposals in
540 the field of performing arts from an artistic and aesthetic approach. Moreover, these authors
541 base the teaching of dance and theatre on the different elements of human movement and
542 expressive factors to discover all the movement possibilities and improve body, space, and
543 time awareness (Ferrari, 2014; Laban, 1984; Schinca, 2010). CBM encourages creativity
544 through expressive games and embodied movements within PE. This method is not aimed at
545 analysing the expressive factors but tries to increase creativity and body awareness.

546 Other authors have implemented expressive content through pedagogical methods or
547 models that are not specific for teaching this content (Levenberg et al., 2020; Méndez-
548 Giménez et al., 2017). These authors have concluded the benefits of these non-specific
549 methods in terms of promoting students' autonomy and responsibility (CBM includes the
550 stage 'Creative composition' that might well encourage autonomy), or the inclusion of
551 reflection times during the lessons (CBM includes an optional last stage for this purpose).
552 Additionally, pedagogical models consider all the elements of the teaching-learning process
553 (i.e., students, teachers, content, and context; Haerens et al., 2011) and are centred on the
554 students, which favour the development of the four learning domains: cognitive, physical,
555 social, and affective (Fernandez-Rio & Iglesias, 2022). So, this paper explores the
556 conceptualisation of a specific pedagogical model for the teaching of expressive content
557 within PE mainly based on a creative and embodied approach.

558 Although previous works highlight many benefits of creative and embodied
559 interventions to improve body expressiveness, there is still no empirical evidence of this
560 pedagogical proposal. Thus, further studies are needed to know the potentialities and

561 limitations of CBM and the effects on the students' creativity, embodiment, basic
562 psychological needs, or cognitive and affective domains. However, in the application of
563 CBM, some limitations of the MbP should be considered. Teachers need training before
564 using MbP and enough time to achieve the intended educational purposes (Fernandez-Rio &
565 Iglesias, 2022). Also, this model could overcome limitations related to the involvement of
566 low-skilled students when applying traditional sports content because expressive content
567 accepts a wide variety of responses independent of their physical ability. Finally, expressive
568 content could be appealing to some students, who could feel motivated to engage in physical
569 activity through expressive activities.

570 To conclude, we would like to summarise what CBM adds to the existing literature:

571 1) this model is designed for a pedagogical context where, to our knowledge, there are no
572 specific pedagogical models to teach expressive content; 2) CBM is focused on working
573 expressive content included in the PE curricula through different games and tasks (e.g.,
574 symbolic and rhythmical games, dance, drama,...); 3) CBM is a student-centred approach
575 that combines direct instruction with improvisation and a creativity-based approach where
576 students have higher autonomy; 4) CBM is also based on exploring different movement
577 possibilities through embodied experiences.

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